

Zybertspheres - Light

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In Zybert Cosmology the universe comprises Zybertspheres, (Z). Ours has an antineutron core, enveloped by a matter-antimatter creation zone, enveloped by a growing expanding spherical neutron cloud. Core gravity, (a), is all pervasive affecting all matter and antimatter and light. (a) acts radially from (Z) centres along the Axis of Zybert and redefines light.

In Zybert Cosmology light has 3 speeds, c - Eigen, \hat{c} - Relative and (C) - Absolute or (Z) speed. c is speed relative to emitters, \hat{c} is speed relative to receivers and (C) is speed relative to (Z) centres fixed in fixed space. c is additive with emitter, receiver and reflector speed, and gravity.

In Zybert Cosmology Doppler shift is expressed as

$$\hat{f} / f = \hat{c} / c \quad \hat{c} = c - v \quad v \text{ is emitter-receiver relative velocity}$$

also, $\Delta \hat{f} / f = \Delta \hat{c} / c$

and, $(\Delta \hat{f} / \Delta t) / f = (\Delta \hat{c} / \Delta t) / c$.

$\Delta \hat{f} / \Delta t$ Hz/s is the parameter JPL calculated from measured Doppler data for Pioneer 10/11

$\Delta \hat{c} / \Delta t$ m/s/s is the relational acceleration of EMR at the detector.

Core gravity, (a), accelerating objects outward is seen as objects receding at $v \sim 7e4 \text{ m/s/Mpc}$. At $r=46.5e9 \text{ ly}$ and $t \sim 14e9 \text{ yrs}$, $v=c$, $\hat{c}=0$, $v=0$, thus light is not visible and this defines the edge of our visible sphere. Beyond the edge, $v > c$, $\hat{c} < 0$, so light cannot reach us.

Light has an Eigen energy, $h\nu$, independent of observed frequency.

Just like mass, light has gravity commensurate with its mass and is also affected by gravity, both of local mass and of the central (Z) core.

For GPS satellites, $\hat{c} > c$ from earth's gravity and $\hat{c} < c$ from satellite velocity in prograde orbits, and are compensated by correcting clock frequency. (a) accelerates light away from (Z) centres like mass is. (a) causes curved light paths like light from Hyades at 153ly, the sun bends light and Neutron spheres stop light, e.g. Sag-A* (8.26e36kg) stops light at 220m altitude.

[1] Zybertspheres - Phenomena.xlsx see <https://zenodo.org/records/17034092>